

Glanders Disease: An Overview

Sejal Antiya^{1*}, Akash Thakor² and Bhavesh Pandor²

¹Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Kamdhenu university, Anand- 388001

²Department of Veterinary Microbiology, Kamdhenu university, Dantiwada- 385506

Introduction

Glanders is an infectious disease caused by the *Burkholderia mallei*. Glanders is primarily a disease affecting horses. It also affects donkeys and mules and can be naturally contracted by other mammals such as goats, dogs, and cats. There are certain synonyms of the disease like Dries, Farcy, Equine nasal phthisis, Maliasmus.

History of disease outbreak

The first recorded history of the glanders disease by Aristotle in 3rd century. Zoonotic potential of the disease transmission from animals to human reported in late 19th century.

History of disease outbreak in India

Year	State	City
2005-06	Maharashtra	Pune, Panchgani
	Punjab	Ludhiana
	Uttar Pradesh	Meerut, Muzaffar nagar, Ghaziabad
	Uttarakhand	Nainital
2007-08	Andhra Pradesh	Mehboobnagar, Balanagar, Rajpur
	Haryana	Karnal
	Himachal Pradesh	Nahan, Sirmour
	Uttarakhand	Haldwani, Nainital
2009-10	Chhattisgarh	Lakhenagar, Raipur
2010-11	Himachal Pradesh	Pandoh, Mandi
	Uttar Pradesh	Ghaziabad, Bijnor
2011-12	Uttar Pradesh	Bulandshar, Kashganj
2012-13	Uttar Pradesh	Auriya, Hardoi
2013-14	Chhattisgarh	Ramnagar, Raipur
	Himachal Pradesh	Solan
	Uttar Pradesh	Badaun, Hardoi
2014-15	Himachal Pradesh	Mandi

	Uttar Pradesh	Agra
	Jammu and Kashmir	Katra
2015-16	Jammu and Kashmir	Katra
	Punjab	Gurdaspur
	Uttar Pradesh	Bandaun, Kasganj, Ghaziabad, Hapur, Shamli
	Uttarakhand	Haridwar, Udham singh nagar
	Gujarat	Ahmedabad, Patan, Kheda
	2016-17	Haryana
Himachal Pradesh		Shapur, Kangra
Jammu and Kashmir		Katra
Uttarakhand		Haridwar, Udham singh nagar
Gujarat		Ahmedabad, Patan, Banaskantha, Bhavnagar, Palitana, Jamnagar, Junagadh, Kutch
Rajasthan		Udaipur, Dholpur
Madhya Pradesh		Laxmiganj, Gwalior

Etiology

Glanders is caused by *Burkholderia mallei*, it is Gram negative, non-motile, non-capsulated and non-spore forming bacteria of the *Burkholderiaceae* family. These bacteria were previously known as *Pseudomonas mallei*.

Epidemiology

Hosts

- Equidae, humans and other species are susceptible
- Donkeys are most susceptible, mules somehow less susceptible and horses are somehow resistance,
- Susceptibility to glanders has been also reported for camels, small ruminant dog and wild animals
- Carnivores may be infected due to eating infected meat
- Glanders is a zoonotic disease (extremely rare) and one recent case has been reported in 2000 U.S.A during laboratory work

Transmission

- Most common source of infection due to ingestion of food or water contaminated by excretion of nasal discharge from carrier animals
- Due to contamination of skin abrasions and mucous membranes, or aerosols
- Certain report of venereal transmission from stallions to mares, and vertical transmission from the mare
- Also spread through fomites
- Use of contaminated equipment's like grooming brushes
- Flies might be as mechanical vectors

Zoonotic aspect of disease:

- **Four forms of infection**

1. **Septicemia:** Fever, chills, myalgia, pleuritic chest pain, generalized erythroderma, jaundice, photophobia, lacrimation, diarrhea and granulomatous or necrotizing lesions. Death usually occurs in 7 to 10 days.
2. **Pulmonary infection:** Pneumonia, pulmonary abscesses and pleural infusions. Incubation period of about 10-14 days.
3. **Acute localized cutaneous infection:** Nodules, abscesses and ulcers in the mucous membranes, skin, lymphatic vessels and subcutaneous tissues
4. **Chronic infection:** Multiple abscesses, nodules or ulcers can be seen in the skin, liver, spleen or muscles

- The case fatality rate is - 95% in untreated cases and more than 50% in treated cases
- The mortality rate for localized disease is 20% in treated
- The overall mortality rate is 40%

Action of physical and chemical reagent on organism

- Sensitive to the external environment and destroyed by exposure to direct sunlight within 24 hrs.
- Destroyed by most of the common disinfectants like sodium hypochlorite and other chlorine compounds, potassium permanganate, copper sulphate, formalin, chlorine, 70% ethanol and 2% glutaraldehyde.
- Killed bacteria by heating to 55°C for 10 minutes

Clinical sign of glanders in animals

There is total 2 form of disease

1. Acute disease

- High fever
- Cough
- Dyspnea
- Thick nasal discharge
- Rapidly spreading ulcers on the nasal mucosa
- Nodules on the skin of lower limbs or abdomen
- Sub maxillary lymph nodes- swollen and painful
- Lymphatic vessels on the face become thickened
- Death in 1 to 2 weeks due to septicemia

2. Chronic disease

Total 3 form of Chronic disease.

1. Pulmonary form:

- Lesions in the lungs develop along with nasal and cutaneous lesions
- Chronic and diffuse pneumonia with severe coughing, dyspnea and epistaxis
- In male animals, glanderous orchitis is a common feature

2. Nasal form:

- Nodules and ulcers on mucosa
- Commence as nodules of about 1 cm.
- Ulcerate and heal as star shaped scars
- Septum may even be perforated.
- Also involve Pharynx and Larynx

3. Cutaneous form:

- Subcutaneous nodules (1-2 cm) which Ulcerate and drain a honey-colored discharge (pus)
- Thickened fistulous lymphatics radiate from the lesions and connect one to the other
- Mainly Cutaneous lesions in medial aspect of the hock, but can occur anywhere in the body
- Lymphadenopathy and cording of lymphatics are common (referred as Farcy pipes)

Clinical sign of glanders in human

- Fever with chills and sweating
- Muscle aches
- Chest pain
- Muscle tightness
- Headache
- Nasal discharge
- Light sensitivity
- tearing of the eyes some time

Prevention and Control of disease

- Suspected animals should be isolate
- Separate the feeding and watering for sick and healthy animals.
- Proper disposal (Bury) of the left-over feed and fodder by the sick animals.
- Separate persons who should be handle sick and healthy animals.
- Bury the dead animal in deep underground away from the farm.
- Keep close eye watch for symptoms like nasal and eye discharges, respiratory problems.
- Hygiene maintained of the farm were outbreak occurs
- Extension programme or awareness programme about glanders disease
- Wash hands with soap and water every time while handling suspected animals.
- Farm should be disinfected with suitable disinfectants like chloride, iodine, mercuric chloride, potassium permanganate, 1% sodium hypochlorite, 70% ethanol and 2% glutaraldehyde etc.
- Wash the contaminated materials with solution of 1-part household bleach (0.5% sodium hypochlorite solution) to 9 parts waters.
- Person having wounds, scratches and abrasions on hands should never handle infected animals.

Treatment

There is no vaccine available for disease. Prevention and control depend on early detection and elimination of affected animals, as well as complete quarantine and disinfection of the area which involved. Treatment is given only in endemic areas but does not reliable. Doxycycline,

tetracycline, gentamicin, streptomycin, were effective in the prevention and treatment of experimental glanders.

Referance

<https://www.cdc.gov/glanders/index.html>

<https://www.oie.int/en/animal-health-in-the-world/animal-diseases/Glanders/>

